

Mapless ground robot navigation in forests through Reinforcement Learning

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Abstract—Due to the complexity and heterogeneity of the landscape, autonomous navigation for ground robots in outdoor unstructured environments still poses many challenges. The main difficulty lies in the wide variety of potential obstacles, thus hindering the possibility to fully and accurately model these types of scenarios. We propose a neural network architecture which, given only 3D LiDAR information and a goal, outputs a velocity command for the low-level navigation controller. The network is trained with reinforcement learning without any assumption on the kinematic model of the vehicle, but taking into account only the inability to perform sideways motion and the physical size of the vehicle. The experiments show convincing results of the architecture, allowing the robot to successfully perform point goal navigation and avoid obstacles with smooth trajectories in simulated challenging outdoor environments.

Index Terms—unmanned ground vehicle, reinforcement learning, autonomous navigation, outdoor unstructured environments, 3D LiDAR

I. INTRODUCTION

The autonomy of mobile robotic platforms has received a significant momentum in recent years, mainly due to the advancements in deep learning and the increased computational power available onboard. There is still a significant gap in autonomy for UGVs (Unmanned Ground Vehicles) in outdoor unstructured environments, such as forests, caves and extraterrestrial planets.

In point goal navigation, an agent must be able to correctly assess the optimal path to traverse, which means understanding the landscape and its possible obstacles. Using semantic models usually implies a computational burden and power consumption that cannot be carried out by smaller autonomous systems, or a large inference time that does not meet the control loop timing requirement.

The lack of labeled datasets of outdoor environments further limits the possibility of training an agent in a supervised manner. Reinforcement learning has the advantage of letting the agent learn through direct interaction with a simulated environment, without the need for large, pre-labeled datasets. The agent learns optimal behavior by exploring various actions and receiving feedback based on the results. The main drawback is that it is highly dependable on simulation fidelity and the exploration of the action space may require a rather long time. Other works, like [5], leverage a 2D LiDAR and

reinforcement learning, but do not offer an end-to-end solution from LiDAR to velocity commands. [1] uses depth images to train a model, but does not generalize to random obstacles.

II. METHODOLOGY

In point goal navigation, the agent has to travel from its initial position to a given goal. In the related literature this is typically achieved with map-based navigation, which involves localizing with respect to the map, then sensing the environment, planning a path, and finally execute the plan. The architecture proposed in this abstract addresses all these steps through a model that given the distance to the target and the direction towards the target, uses the raw readings from a 3D LiDAR to output the velocity commands for the low-level navigation controller. The model is able to distinguish and avoid a diverse set of obstacles, thus enabling the agent to navigate in challenging outdoor environments.

A. Simulation Environment

The model is trained with MIDGARD [4], our custom simulator for outdoor robot navigation based on Unreal Engine, in a reinforcement learning framework based on Stable Baselines 3 [2]. The simulator allows total control on the parameters of the 3D LiDAR (i.e. resolution and field of view) and the simulated scenario (i.e. obstacle types -rocks, trees, trunks- and density, weather condition, etc.). A custom Stable Baseline environment was also developed for training multiple agents at the same time, which do not to interact with each other, significantly decreasing training time.

The simulated 3D LiDAR in our experiments outputs 200×30 points at each step, spanning 220° and 40° along the horizontal and the vertical field of view.

B. Network Architecture

The model is comprised of a shallow CNN feature extractor, with two 2D convolutions, that receive as input the 3D LiDAR information. The output of the LiDAR feature extractor is concatenated to the current distance from the target, which is calculated with the Euclidean distance between the agent's and the target's position referred to a common world frame, which is given by:

$$d = \|\mathbf{p}_{\text{agent}} - \mathbf{p}_{\text{target}}\|$$

and the angular difference between the current forward direction of the robot and the robot-target joining segment, which is encoded with the sine and cosine values of the angle:

$$s = \frac{\mathbf{v}_{\text{agent}} \times \mathbf{v}_{\text{seg}}}{\|\mathbf{v}_{\text{agent}}\| \|\mathbf{v}_{\text{seg}}\|}$$

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Fig. 1. Number of Agents Succeeding per Episode

Fig. 2. The proposed network architecture

$$c = \frac{\mathbf{v}_{\text{agent}} \cdot \mathbf{v}_{\text{seg}}}{\|\mathbf{v}_{\text{agent}}\| \|\mathbf{v}_{\text{seg}}\|}$$

where $\mathbf{v}_{\text{seg}} = \mathbf{p}_{\text{agent}} - \mathbf{p}_{\text{target}}$. This is then followed by a fully connected network, that converges to the output, which is the linear and angular velocity. The full network architecture is shown in Fig. 2.

III. RESULTS

A. Training

The model is trained with the PPO (Proximal Policy Optimization) algorithm [3], an on-policy algorithm that optimizes policies by balancing exploration and exploitation through clipped objective functions. Since the kinematics and the embodiment of the actual agent are not considered as we prioritize sample efficiency, the simulator at each timestep translates the agent, checking if there are collisions. The maximum velocity of the simulated vehicle is 1 m s^{-1} .

The model was trained on a NVIDIA RTX 2080ti for 46 hours, with an average simulation steps per second of 210, training with 100 agents in parallel. The agents were trained using a difficulty curriculum, where the obstacle density is increased whenever more than 80% of the agents reached the target without colliding.

The reward function has been tuned so that the robot learns both to go towards the target and not to hit an obstacle. This is done by increasing the negative reward due to collisions of the robot as the difficulty increases, so that at the start the robot prioritize reaching the target, and later on to not crash.

A plot of the number of agents that are able to reach the target for each episode is reported in Fig. 1. Each dashed line represents an increase in difficulty. Some interesting behaviours can be observed: with less obstacles at the beginning it is able to learn very fast how to reach the target, as it is likely it essentially relies on the information about the distance and the angle, and not the LiDAR. Then, as the obstacle

TABLE I
MODEL EVALUATION RESULTS

Obstacle Density	Success Ratio
10%	0.98
30%	0.95
50%	0.87
70%	0.75
100%	0.65

density increases, the number of agents that reach the target decreases, as the agent’s policy must learn to rely also on the 3D LiDAR, which takes more time to train, as the number of parameters relative to LiDAR section is much higher. From the episode 200 the graph shows an improving trend, confirming the policy has learnt the contribution of the 3D LiDAR. In the end the number of agents succeeding decreases, as probably the density of obstacles is making the agent take more time to reach the target, thus resulting in unsuccessful episodes.

B. Model Evaluation

To evaluate the performance of the model, we have tested it with different difficulties. For each difficulty step the agent is spawned randomly 100 times at a fixed distance from the target, and evaluated if it is able or not to reach the target. The results are reported in Table I.

As it can be observed the model shows an appreciable success rate even when the environment is very dense of obstacles (namely above 50%). There results make us confident on exploring future architectures including also RGB data for semantic understanding of the scene.

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